

The Role of Social Networking in Global Trade

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Abstract:

Objectives: This study aims to clarify the effects of social networking in global trade, thus explaining the overview of social networking, the significance of social networking in trade development and its challenges of social networking in global trade environments, the interaction.

Methodology: This study used the analytical approach and the descriptive approach to administrative legislation related to the subject of the study.

Results: The explosion of internet tools and social networking has as big an impact on trade information and the Commercial operations all over the world which can facilitate the improved trade productivity and development by enhancing the communication and collaboration of Commercial frameworks, which aids knowledge transfer and consequently makes trade more effective. thus, global commercial es and merchants should provide training through general education courses and lifelong learning and provide the necessary Information and Communication Technology (ICT) skills for all employees to enhance their knowledge to deal with these new technologies in the social media age. Understanding the role of social networking will significantly enhance the organizational performance and achieve commercial goals in global commercial environments.

Keywords: Social Networking, Trade, Merchants, global trade

1 Introduction

Social network has transformed the global trade by providing new opportunities for merchant, companies and commercial organizations to connect with customers and expand their reach into new markets. Social media globalization impacted the way commercial work, commercial contracting and scope of trade in the global marketplace that's because social media channels enable merchants and commercial companies to reach customers around the international marketplace, while customers get to shop for their needs from anywhere at any time and they save their effort and time.

with Global social media keeps evolving and expanding in the trade world the role of commercial legislation in become locally and internationally a must in order to facilitate commercial commercial among the world specially that that social media trends become the shape commercial organizations working in the global landscape today.

2 The nature of Commercial networking

The role of social media has grown in recent years to enter various aspects of individuals and not limit themselves to the social boundaries for which it was originally created, to include many sectors of life, including the commercial sector. These platforms have become an essential feature in the world of digital marketing, which has affected many commercial companies, merchants and brands. Commercial companies are seeking to use these electronic social media as marketing platforms for their trade with the target audience, and exploiting them to deliver various commercial messages.

Social commerce or commerce through social networking sites means the method of buying and selling goods or commercial services directly through merchants, companies, or stores integrated into social media platforms. This model moves social media beyond its traditional role among individuals in the discovery process by completing the entire purchasing process without leaving their favorite applications.

Social commerce is a term that refers to the use of social media platforms for buying and selling products and services. It encompasses a wide range of activities, from social shopping where consumers can purchase directly from social media posts, to social network-driven referrals and reviews that influence purchasing decisions. The concept of social commerce also includes features such as social shopping carts, social group buying, and peer-to-peer sales facilitated by social networking sites. This fusion of e-commerce and social media has transformed the way businesses interact with their customers, as well as how consumers discover and engage with brands and products.

Here, it must be pointed out that the use of social media in commerce was through the search engine Yahoo in 2005 when it promoted some popular commercial products within the Shops platform. Then this concept began to expand commercially to include providing various advice and support from specialized experts to help consumers during the simple or more complex purchasing process, and this trade continues to exist until now through e-commerce operations on various social networking sites.[1], [2],[3],

2.1 The concept of Commercial networking

Trade networking is the practice of building relationships with individuals, merchants and companies for commercial purposes. It includes marketing, advertising, exchanging information and completing commercial operations that can be beneficial to both parties by conducting trade networking in person or online through social media or through a combination of both. Through repeated interactions, merchants and commercial es create deeper connections with those interested in transacting commercial.

The idea of using social media in commerce is based mainly on presenting commerce content in its various forms on social media sites in the form of messages published on multiple platforms. The methods of electronic commercial promotion vary to include still or animated images, live or recorded video clips supported by text, or even just Texts related to commercial products or services or through influencers through social media. The content provided, in any form, aims to have direct and abundant access to the audience and create interaction with them to promote their trade, enhance sales and expand the scope of trade. The displayed publications and videos contain direct links from merchants or commercial companies to the payment interface and its mechanisms, allowing users to complete the purchase process in the easiest ways.

2.2 Types of stores on social commerce

With the growing role of social media in supporting commerce, Facebook, Instagram, and Pinterest have launched official tools to promote commerce through their social networks and to simplify the concept of commerce and shopping via Internet media. Other social networks, such as YouTube and Twitter, did not hesitate to enter this commercial field and experiment with ways to add stores to their platforms. These features work by creating digital storefronts that are visible to followers organically or with paid ads. [4].[5]. [6].

2.3 Commercial Limitations of on Social Commerce sites

Merchants and commercial companies that use social media in their trade are generally limited to simple trade, which in this type of trade does not exceed the value of the products 100 - 1000 US dollars, because the majority of those dealing in this type of trade originally go to these sites to communicate with friends, search and view content that interests them. Therefore, when they buy high-value products or services, they go to other than these websites. Consumers usually do not buy expensive or high-priced products and services without prior planning, whether online or directly in stores, and therefore products and services in this form do not achieve high sales on social networking sites. There is also a greater risk when purchasing high-value products and services over the Internet before seeing them in person from their owners. On the other hand, social media remains a means of reaching them to promote and introduce what merchants and commercial companies offer as a type of advertising and marketing to reach the largest number of individuals.⁷

Because of the impressive speed of social media growth, the customer data grows remarkably quickly. The better you know your customers' wishes, the better you can align your offerings. Consequently, the products or the marketing campaign, be it excelling or not, can be developed in line with users' wishes. To understand this is always a speed advantage. It can come quickly to the product release on the national market first, then practically around the world. Transport is not a problem, why? Because with the same speed, international trade can also take place thanks to social media.⁸

Aren't all of the possibilities of social media so far just lovely? Yes, indeed, there are many indeed. Thus, if you begin to use social media for global trade, there are lots of opportunities to be discovered for everyone. The first advantage, of course, is not timeliness. For it immediately offers the prospect of attracting customers and generating sales. There's no ad in the world that quickly, for example, after an event. It's similar with Twitter, Facebook, or LinkedIn. In addition to immediate benefits like this, social media even has a long-term advantage. If you set up your business on one or more platforms, you are soon learning more about social media, and even about your company's marketing, or creating entrepreneurial harmony. What's next? You can get ready through the power of self to trade globally.⁹

Given these limitations, firms will have to decide whether it is still worthwhile to use likes in order to trigger a less wrong set of trade actions than would have been the case without a complement to past export performance. As social media platforms like Facebook, Twitter, and Instagram continue to change their engagement formula that controls who sees content, firms need strategies to retain visibility even as concentrated engagement formulas expand the cost of maintaining a presence in the social media market across the board. For now, only some firms have such strategies because social media marketing might require a unique mix of standard capabilities, some of which are usually associated with firms in the ICT industry, as further analysis of firm visibility will reveal. A growing body of literature implies that addressing these challenges head-on can make social media marketing tools effective in engaging and entering new customers, as long as innovative digital experiences are readily delivered to the right audience¹⁰.

Since its inception, social media platforms like Facebook, Twitter, LinkedIn, and Pinterest have made a significant impact in the consumer market. Many consumers turn to social media to make purchasing decisions, but it has also brought about challenges. For example, identifying fraudulent goods has been a big challenge, resulting in a longer buying process. Another challenge is that companies find it hard to identify the return on investment from advertising through social media. With the global trend of avoiding flashy adverts, companies struggle to compete for the attention of potential customers. Additionally, there is more communication on social media than with the consumer, and there is no guarantee that customers will purchase a product based on their interaction with the company. For most third-world countries, exposing themselves to the global market without proper preparation might be regrettable. The limited use of the English language puts them at a disadvantage compared to native English-speaking countries. It is also important to note that the privacy and security of social media platforms can never be guaranteed.¹¹

3 Legal frame of social media Influence on consumer

The higher the gender and level of education, especially among householders and business employees, the more social media provides benefits that support the consumer's decision to purchase a product.

In addition, the results of retailers' business expansion were obtained through the digitalization of storefronts, resulting in a 2 percent increase in customers. Social media also makes e-commerce an attractive option that must be implemented with strategic policy momentum for retailers in first and second-tier cities. This is due to the ease of remembering, discussing, and working on products within tribes. By adopting a social marketing policy, online retailers can effectively target the consumer market.

Different channels, such as Facebook, Twitter, or YouTube, can be used by consumers as sources of information and entertainment in their daily lives. Facebook, Instagram, and Twitter are considered the most suitable social media channels for interacting with consumers in both personal and professional dimensions. Recommendations for specific products can be made interactively based on consumer feedback, as consumers share their beliefs, attitudes, and values about a proposed issue. This impacts the customer's decision to purchase the product.

Previous studies have shown that the use of social media increased online store purchases by 13.2 percent, purchase intention by 4.2 percent, and offline store purchase intention by 0.8 percent. Social media also increased shares by 211 percent, communications by 204 percent, and comments by 202 percent. Social media provides communication channels that affect online stores accessible through the same platform, triggering consumer interest and influencing their buying behavior.

Research conducted by Kundan Das and Anup Krish aimed to determine the influence of social media on consumer behavior. The findings concluded that consumers are able to access information from the internet and other social media sources, such as social networks and blogs, which provide an overview of the product before purchasing. Customers can also express their opinions, recommendations, and suggestions for retailers to improve the quality of their products.

Social media has become very influential in terms of disseminating information and building consumer awareness. According to the Associated Chambers of Commerce and Industry of India, 35 percent of consumers engage in the same way as they experience on online e-commerce platforms. Therefore, they mostly research products through search engines so that retailers should be ready to answer their queries.

3.1 Social media as a source of product information

Most academic studies of electronic word-of-mouth have tried to answer how to spread particular information within a network because companies can add significant economic value. Thus, companies have adopted a range of web-based distribution and information-gathering mechanisms. For instance, they gave employees greater freedom to create, edit, and publish wiki-based documents ranging from technical specifications to standard operating procedures to help manage corporate information flows. Besides, firms adopted sophisticated "channel information management tools" to configure, aggregate and filter web-based product information to suit different client preferences faster with better quality and to instantly help clients compare the product offerings of the companies.¹²

Trade is largely about information. Information shapes individuals' opinions and, therefore, their valuation of a particular good or service. Since the Uruguay Round Agreements were signed and the World Trade Organization was set up in 1995, the pace and scope of international trade negotiations has increased. However, the Agreement on Trade Related Aspects of Intellectual Property provides protection only to the legal owners of intellectual property and requires all signatory nations to ensure that dispute resolution machinery is in place to protect property rights. Both the creators and end users of intellectual property are situated in a wider network of actors who are more inclined than the others to spread news about new products or value them more positively, such as the supply chain actors known to the creators, members of a club, or the residents of countries.

3.2 Impact of online reviews and recommendations

Online reviews continue to have a significant effect on product sales in both online and offline contexts. A positive review can boost sales, and a negative review can decrease sales. Factors that increase the impact of an online review include the size of the reviewing audience, the perceived expertise of the reviewer, and the emotional involvement of the reviewer. Reviews credited as helpful are also more impactful. Reviews also change customer decision. A study conducted by Forrester Research on behalf of Oracle in 2014 showed that 70% of respondents stated that online reviews are very or somewhat important to purchasing decisions, and 81% of those have made purchase decisions based on social media feedback. Furthermore, there have been results showing that 92% of consumers in the USA ignore email or text-based recommendations, while 92% of consumers also trust recommendations from individuals known to them personally, and 70% trust consumer opinions.¹³

The internet has turned the world into a global village with almost instantaneous informative, educational, and commercial transactions. E-commerce has brought an ease and swiftness that was unimaginable two decades ago. This global trade is not only driven by the demand but also through the supply as small and medium-scale enterprises (SMEs) are tech-savvy and using various platforms (such as group orders from social media and personal websites) and tools that e-commerce platforms provide to attract buyers and gain market access. Thus, firms with sales strategies using digital platforms can sell globally, and this global trade has increased due to the availability and ease of shipping and by the usage of intermediaries that simplify methods of payment, customs procedures, and also provide online workflows. Consequently, in recent years, most of the world's biggest retailers have invested heavily in their online presence to reach global markets. Facebook, Instagram, and Pinterest are some of the platforms where they set up their stores as these channels have also become successful for customer reputation through reviews and recommendations.¹⁴

3.3 Social media influencers and brand endorsements

Social media influencers usually provide a great way to reach an active engaged audience. This is believed to have built a strong level of trust amongst their followers. Studies have also found that more than 80% of those who follow social media influencers said that they usually trust their recommendations

over those by celebrities. As per Joris Heuberghs, marketing professor at Turkey's Bilkent University stated, "for many, it is difficult to understand how and why someone would trust a social media influencer more than traditional advertising tools. However, the point is not to simply connect a good product with a likable social media influencer, instead the actual value comes when the influencer and the product share values that the influencers' followers appreciate. This is what most brands hope to achieve. When done correctly, an influencer could not only provide one with access to a mass following, but drive real action too, such as ultimately leading to sales".

An influencer is defined as "a person with the ability to influence potential buyers of a product or service by promoting or recommending the items on social media". They usually have a common theme of interest which is used to harness their popularity, enabling them to convey marketing messages to a large audience which would otherwise be very costly to reach.

Social media has resulted in the emergence of a new breed of entrepreneurs. One popular form of monetizing social media is through influencers. The rise in the attractiveness of social media following as a marketing tool can be gauged by the rise in expenditure on influencers. Between 2016 and 2017, businesses spent more than \$570 million. The projection for 2019 was \$1.6 billion and by 2020 it is set to be a whopping \$2.38 billion U.S. dollars.¹⁵

4 Role of social network in shaping global trade policies

Global trade in services increased at a rate much higher than the traditional goods trade in the past few years. The trading partners were found to be from geographically dispersed regions. As per WTO reports, the global trade in services in 2019, 2020 and 2021 in 2018, witnessed a growth of 20%, 1.2% and 2.3% respectively, while the goods trade decreased by 5% in 2019 and improved by 8% in 2020. This pattern continued for many years. A number of country governments came up with fiscal and non-fiscal trade promotion packages to help their firms involved in these operations. Still, many firms started investing more in the services trade when possible, and the segment witnessed high growth. E-commerce and its associated operations received high attention, and government policies controlled and regulated the operations. In the initial days, it was argued that ensuring high global trade in services would lower the carbon footprint and ensure protection of renewable and non-renewable resources, as a person who stays at home would adopt frugal lifestyles. Also, the e-commerce firms would deliver at the doorstep without the need for a person to travel.

The role of social media in shaping public opinion and influencing decision making is gaining prominence across all walks of life. Be it citizens protesting against authoritarian rule and Arab Spring movements; dissatisfaction with government's urban planning (Citizens movements in India); Pink Chaddi in India 2009 to protest against right-wing moral policing in Mangalore – Kerala case; or the spontaneous protest against government's policies in all countries – grant anti-globalization – it was social media in general, Facebook and Twitter in particular, which was instrumental in bringing together the physically dispersed entities into a single coordinated action. There is ample evidence to prove the instrumental role played by these social media in this transformation. Most importantly, when introducing a disruptive economic policy like the Aadhar Card in India in 2018, where the government expects every resident in the country to have a 100% compliant bank account; the social media including WhatsApp played havoc among the uneducated lower strata public. Issues like loss of privacy by linking their Aadhar card with bank account, fears related to the possible isolation from the general society were systematically fed in by the social media.

4.1 Public opinion and activism and government regulations and policies

In a similar vein, stress the growing role of social media, including platforms such as Facebook and MySpace, in understanding consumer behavior, calling the resulting shift as radical as utmost famous Schumpeterian innovations. In news media, these same platforms created a more interactive, consumers-as-co-creators model. In our context true, in 2007, Apple announced via mainstream media various prototype iPads, counting also a model with a stylus. Criticism on social media forced Apple CEO Steve Jobs to establish a more interactive, robust innovation process.

The smartphone revolution and the explosion of social media have reinvented how firms and the public interact and, in particular, how the public exerts pressure on firms. Perhaps the most dramatic impact concerns CSR. As showed, social media dramatically impacted two campaigns on opposite sides of CSR issues: in 2009, consumer pressure on Nestlé forced it to up its game on palm oil sustainability; in

2010, consumer pressure on BP forced it to stop playing Greenpeace at its own outdoor game. Moreover, spillovers on other stakeholders or industries are not unusual. For example, the moratorium imposed in 2010-11, roughly at the same time as the BP pressure (losing '40+ billion in market value in 50 days) - forced the UK cabinet to shield petroleum companies from similar disruptions when the US parent company could impose 3rd party liabilities.¹⁶

Though there are fewer regulations to consider over social media platforms, as a rising amount of various types of information moves via the internet, sophisticated information distribution networks that are fueled by web-based techniques have implicated greater proper judgments within countries. In India, China, the United Kingdom, and across the US, regulatory bodies are also coming to grips with the possibilities and influences of information distribution in their areas. Conversely, one of the most important challenges faced by social media regulations has been expanding regulatory rulings via commercial fields, regions, and countries, particularly when borders cross. Such pressures increase the importance for institutions to modify business procedures in order to lessen the possibility of unclear legal activities and the antagonistic effects of stricter legislation.

Policy development and regulatory action on digital technologies have been slow to keep pace with technological advances in social media, leading to regulatory fragmentation and inconsistencies both within and among countries. One of the biggest and relatively unique challenges associated with the global nature of social media platforms is the development of interlinked regulatory policies across national boundaries. Governments around the world are working to create regulations to best manage the way data and technology are managed. With the advent of cross-border data floods, robotic information strategies, and internet-enabled phony news, national and global regulating bodies may confront new regulatory inquiries. National regulatory authorities are also involved in attempts to monitor the use of social media sites and their assets within the country.

4.2 Trade agreements and negotiations

In 2015, a \$800m, 10-year partnership was created between the US and India, where US ambassadors in 24 American cities invited Indian business executives to seminars. The \$10m Indian Enterprise And Investment Centre, based in Mumbai, figures at the core of this partnership. Over the time period, the enterprise aims to take advantage of the enormous networks of trade, industry, and government officials both in India and North America.

In November 2017, the new blockchain network IOI-Blockchain was created by Investree, an AI-powered event ecosystem accelerator, making it possible for businesses in Asia to better use new technologies.

In November 2017, the international law firm Shearman & Sterling recruited three partners and several associates to establish an office in South Korea. The firm's new team has spearheaded the \$300m investment to be made by HDL in Samil PwC Special Situations Investment Management Co. Ltd - one of Korea's largest investment firms.¹⁷

In May 2017, the United Nations Commission on International Trade Law established the Working Group III on Online Dispute Resolution. Cambodia has created a task force to lead the preparations to be a member of the Association of Southeast Asian Nations Digital Integration Index. Japan has expressed its interest in collaborating with Cambodia on a digital payment system. Telecommunications technologies have also been expanded to Russia, Africa, Asia, and the Pacific.

The use of social media by governments to communicate with people is on the rise. At present, over 140 countries provide their citizens with online platforms where they can obtain information on trade, smuggling, and related agreements. The spread of digital technology is also helping advance trade negotiations among countries and states.

4.3 Social media platforms and their impact on global trade

In global trade, risk management systems can be built on news, views, and celebrity endorsements circulated in social media. When national borders are poorly defined, social media news is used to raise the cost of cross-border trade, which affects who buys which assets. When these costs become sufficiently high, better information must be provided in social media, which involves underwriting first-time arrivals and risky transactions. Additionally, the advent of social media has spawned a multiplicity of social and business-related websites sharing citizen concerns, business operations, and threats, as well as government actions that have taken steps to promote information exchange through trade and highlight tradeoffs to avoid protecting infirmities or promoting growth strategies (disasters in the form of revolving asset traps). The three papers under review are therefore selected to reflect different facets of global trade and the potential of social media.

The number of social media platforms has grown to several billion users over the past 20 years. Social media users are no longer just communicating, but also creating and sharing user-generated content, participating in various topic discussions or online communities, and creating weak social ties between users with common interests, activities, or backgrounds. Social media platforms are increasingly becoming an important source of information, particularly in the field of global trade. Social media impacts global trade by affecting information exchange, decision making, innovation, and trust in trading partners. This paper reviews the literature on social media and its impact on global trade topics, including 1) risk management in global trade, portfolio equifinality and institutional knowledge sharing in global trade, 2) the creation and deployment of products and services for use or application in economic and trading systems within global trade networks, and 3) production, export, importing activity, and behaviors of firms involved in global trade within global trade marketing systems, respectively.

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5 Conclusion

Keeping up with technological developments, especially with regard to social networking networks in life, has become a reality, and the purposes of their use have evolved until they include the world of commerce and have become an important and essential means for many commercial operations, especially in the field of international trade. There is no doubt that social media has taken the lead and received great attention from traders and trading experts. This necessitated studying the impact and repercussions of using social media in the field of trade. On other hand the study, was important to understand the context dynamics of each startup and to understand in depth the challenges that are posed throughout this process, but it offers clear limitations in the generalization of its results.

This study has yielded several findings and recommendations, summarized as follows:

5.1 Results

1. Social media is not only used by companies as a marketing medium, but is also used to access information about their market, competitors and customers as a tool to improve business performance and innovation
2. With the rise of social media globalization, it has become easier for organizations to create and maintain international relationships with their customers, collaborators, and partners, by breaking down distance and language barriers and traders who are able to engage in social trading networks want to gain an edge by using "the wisdom of crowds.
3. The trading via social networks can get complicated. This is especially the case when users have to contend with the full institutional experience. That institutional experience is rife with jargon, complex explanations, and a lack of solid evidence for certain trading decisions

5.2 Recommendations

1. We recommend allowing the integration of social media into business operations, similar to e-commerce.
2. We recommend that merchants prepare their infrastructure and human resources and ensure their readiness for the new stage in the modern digital commerce process
3. We recommend that the Jordanian legislator amend the necessary legislation to establish a specific legal framework for such decisions.
4. It is necessary to ensure the necessary technical protection for trade, especially against cyber attacks.

6. References

1. S Rizwan, HA Al-Malkawi, K Gadar... - ... International Journal of ..., 2021 - emerald.com. Impact of brand equity on purchase intentions: empirical evidence from the health takāful industry of the United Arab Emirates. [emerald.com](https://www.emerald.com)
2. RFS Syafrinaldi, H Susanti - ICoSEEH 2019, 2020 - researchgate.net. Legal Reforms of Trademarks in Order to Increase Investment in Indonesia. [researchgate.net](https://www.researchgate.net)
- 3 The State Council of the People Republic Of China Next Generation Artificial Intelligence Development Plan July 2017.
- 4 Dr. Latifa Jabari, The Role of Artificial Intelligence Models in Decision Making, published research, Journal of Human Sciences, University Center Tindouf - Algeria, Issue 1, 2017, p. 122.
- 5 See Article 2 of the Jordanian Electronic Transactions Law No. 15 of 2015, published in the Official Gazette No. 5341, on page No. 5292 dated 17-5-2015.
- 6 See Article 1 of the UAE Electronic Transactions and Commerce Law No. 1 of 2006, published in the Official Gazette No. 442 - Year 36 - dated January 31, 2006.
- 7 JA Leggett - UNFCCC: New York, NY, USA, 2020 - everycrsreport.com. The United Nations framework convention on climate change, the Kyoto protocol, and the Paris agreement: a summary. [everycrsreport.com](https://www.everycrsreport.com)
- ⁸ S Rizwan, HA Al-Malkawi, K Gadar... - ... International Journal of ..., 2021 - emerald.com. Impact of brand equity on purchase intentions: empirical evidence from the health takāful industry of the United Arab Emirates. [emerald.com](https://www.emerald.com)
- ⁹ V Grewe, A Gangoli Rao, T Grönstedt, C Xisto... - Nature ..., 2021 - nature.com. Evaluating the climate impact of aviation emission scenarios towards the Paris agreement including COVID-19 effects. [nature.com](https://www.nature.com)
- ¹⁰ Aloun , D. D. M. . (2022). The Jordanian Constitutional Court: The Legal Function. *American Journal of Social and Humanitarian Research*, 3(7), 141–154. <https://doi.org/10.31150/ajshr.v3i7.1351>
- ¹¹ A Rachman, D Hendrawan - Journal of Advances in Humanities ..., 2021 - tafpublications.com. Legal protection of brand rights for franchise agreements in Indonesia. [tafpublications.com](https://www.tafpublications.com)
- ¹² Dema Matruk Aloun, Zarqa University, Social Trading Tools Research · May 2024 DOI: [10.13140/RG.2.2.28760.10246](https://doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.28760.10246)
- ¹³ L Wegener - Transnational Environmental Law, 2020 - cambridge.org. Can the Paris agreement help climate change litigation and vice versa?. [cambridge.org](https://www.cambridge.org)
- ¹⁴ Dema Matruk Aloun, Zarqa University Women's Economic Empowerment, April 2024, DOI:[10.13140/RG.2.2.30097.44649](https://doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.30097.44649)
- ¹⁵ K Kammel, J Kennedy, D Cermak, M Manoukian - AIPLA QJ, 2021 - HeinOnline. Responsibility for the sale of trademark counterfeits online: Striking a balance in secondary liability while protecting consumers. [msu.edu](https://www.msu.edu)
- ¹⁶ Women in Trade. Dr. Dema Matouk Aloun. Faculty of Law, Zarqa University, Zarqa, Jordan. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.11001210> May 4, 2024
- ¹⁷ Dr. Dema Matruk Aloun. (2022). THE INTERACTIONS OF REFUGEES, HUMAN RIGHTS, AND INTERNATIONAL LAW IN JORDAN. *World Bulletin of Management and Law*, 10, 76-84. Retrieved from <https://scholarexpress.net/index.php/wbml/article/view/988>
- ¹⁸ Rauch, James, E. 2001. "Business and Social Networks in International Trade." *Journal of Economic Literature*, 39 (4): 1177–1203.